

Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Selected Integrated Pest Management Components in Controlling Cabbage Aphid (*Brevicoryne brassicae* Linn.) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) Under Open Field Conditions

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Abstract

This experiment was conducted in the fields of the College of Agriculture / University of Karbala on a cabbage crop during the growing season of 2024/2025. The aim was to evaluate the efficacy of certain integrated pest management components, specifically three botanical pesticides (Palizin, Tondexir, and Oxymatrine) and a bacterial biopesticide (Amyloland), as well as the synergistic effect of combining these components for the control of the cabbage aphid, *Brevicoryne brassicae*, under open field conditions. At the recommended concentration of 3 mL/L, Palizin demonstrated the highest mortality rate among the plant-derived insecticides, achieving a relative efficacy of 91.28% by day 21 post-application. In comparison, Tondexir and Oxymatrine yielded mortality rates of 72.48% and 73.3%, respectively. For Amyloland, the concentration of 3 g/L proved most effective, with a mortality rate of 67.2%, outperforming the 2 g/L and 2.5 g/L treatments, which resulted in 51.2% and 56.9% mortality, respectively. Regarding synergistic interactions, the combination of Palizin + Amyloland was superior, achieving complete aphid control (100% mortality) at 7, 14, and 21 days after application. This treatment outperformed both Tondexir + Amyloland and Oxymatrine + Amyloland, which recorded mortality rates of 76.7%, 94.7%, and 100%, and 80.3%, 99.4%, and 100%, respectively, over the same time intervals.

Keywords: *Brevicoryne brassicae*, Plant-based insecticides, IPM, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*.

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Introduction

Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. capitata L.) is commonly found in the Brassicaceae family – a family that include many of commercial vegetable crops. These are including cauliflower (*B. oleracea* var. botrytis), broccoli (*B. oleracea* var. italica), and raphano (*Raphanus sativus*), turnip (*Brassica rapa* subsp. rapa), and rocket (*Eruca sativa*) (German et al., 2023). Nutritionally valuable, the cabbage leaves have been reported to have rich phytochemical, indispensable nutritive substances, and effective antioxidant compounds (Liao et al., 2021). Although cabbage aphid (*Brevicoryne brassicae*) is the major pest of cabbage and cruciferous vegetables including cauliflower, broccoli and mustard (Patel et al., 2024; Abu-Duka et al., 2025). They

are known for the two small tube-like structures at the back of the body, which are visible under a hand lens. The unmonitored or excessive use of artificial chemical pesticides has caused pollution of the environment and contributed to the negative effects on human health and non-targets (Abu-Duka and Mohammadali, 2021; Abdulwahid and Mohammadali, 2021). Alternatively, the use of plant-based insecticides has been encouraged because of their lesser toxicity to humans and animals, repellent and lethal effects on females (Aimad et al., 2022; Kashmar and Mohammadali, 2024).

With the aim of finding alternative methods that are safer for humans and the environment and less costly to combat harmful insect pests, this study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of plant-based pesticides (Palizin, Tondexir and Oxymatrine) and the commercial bacterial preparation Amyloland (*Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*) in controlling the cabbage aphid *Brevicoryne brassicae* under open field conditions.

Materials and Methods

Field Preparation and Insecticides Used in the Study

The experiment was carried out in the agricultural fields of the College of Agriculture, University of Karbala, using the cabbage cultivar *Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata* L. (cv. Globe Master) (Figure 1). The total area designated for planting was 25×5 m². The soil was prepared, ditches were opened, and seedlings were transferred to the experiment site on November 26, 2024, in six rows (rows), each 23 square meters long. The distance between rows was 90 cm, and the distance between seedlings was 60 cm. Standard agronomic practices, including tillage, field cleaning, weed removal, and foliar fertilization, were applied uniformly across the field. Three plant-based insecticides and one bacterial-based bioinsecticide were used in the study as listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Tested Plant-Based Insecticides and Bacterial Formulation, Their Chemical Groups, and Mixing Rates

Trade name	Chemical group	Active ingredient	Mixing rate (mL or g L ⁻¹)
Palizin 65%SL	Coconut oil soap	Botanical pesticides	3ml
Tondexir 80%EC	Garlic and red pepper	Botanical pesticides	3ml
Oxymatrine 2.4 % SL	Oxymatrine	Tetracyclo-Quinolizidine	3ml
Amyloland 2.2 b./ g	Biological agent	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	2-3 gr.

Figure 1. Agricultural Fields of the College of Agriculture, University of Karbala

Evaluation of the Relative Efficacy of Plant-Based Insecticides and the Bacterial Bio-Insecticide

Concentrations of plant-based pesticides were prepared at 3 ml/L and bacterial bio pesticides at three concentrations: 2, 2.5, and 3 g/L. After severe infestation with the squash aphid, infected squash plants were sprayed. A 5-liter sprayer was used after calibration. The experiment was conducted with three replicates for each concentration, with each replicate containing 10 plants as experimental units. A randomized block design (RCBD) was used to calculate the relative efficacy of the tested pesticides. The equation of Telton and Henderson (1955) was used.

$$\text{Effectiveness}(\%) = 100 \times \left(1 - \frac{\text{Number of pest individuals before treatment} \times \text{Number in control after treatment}}{\text{Number of pest individuals after treatment} \times \text{Number in control before treatment}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Results and Discussion

Evaluation of the Relative Efficacy of Plant-Based Insecticides

The results indicated that among the tested plant-based insecticides—Palizin, Tondexir, and Oxymatrine—applied at the recommended concentration of 3 mL/L, Palizin was the most effective, achieving the highest mortality rate with a relative efficacy of 91.28% at 21 days post-treatment. This significantly exceeded the performance of Tondexir (72.48%) and Oxymatrine (73.3%) at the same evaluation period.

Notably, the 14-day interval showed particularly striking results for Palizin, which reached complete efficacy (100% mortality). In contrast, Tondexir and Oxymatrine showed lower efficacy rates of 89.4% and 85.6%, respectively, during the same evaluation period.

Figure 2. Relative efficacy of three plant-based insecticides at a concentration of 3 mL/L against *B. brassicae*

Note: LSD 0.05 :Concentrations = 8.7 Days = 6.50 Interaction = 12.10

The insecticidal activity of the plant-based compounds Palizin and Tondexir is attributed to their content of secondary metabolites, such as essential oils and bioactive alkaloids. These compounds possess the ability to penetrate and diffuse through insect tissues in a manner similar to conventional insecticides. They also act through direct contact with the insect's body surface, where the chemical constituents penetrate the insect cuticle via the thin tissue layers, ultimately causing paralysis and death (Afifi, 2000).

Plant-derived insecticides contain toxic alkaloids and active substances that inhibit feeding behavior, leading to insect mortality. These compounds may also enter through the respiratory openings, affecting

both the digestive and nervous systems (Romeilah et al., 2010). Oxymatrine, another plant-based insecticide, exerts its effect primarily on the insect nervous system by disrupting chemical signal transmission. It enhances the enzymatic activity of acetylcholinesterase and phenol oxidase, leading to paralysis, impaired respiration, and eventual insect death (Sineria, 2016; Yahya and Mohammadali, 2023).

Synergistic Effect between the Bacterial Formulation and Plant-Based Insecticides

The results in Table (3) show the relative efficacy of the synergistic interaction between the commercial bacterial formulation Amyloland at a concentration of 2 g/L and three plant-based insecticides—Palizin, Tondexir, and Oxymatrine—at a concentration of 2 mL/L against the cabbage aphid. The combination of Palizin + Amyloland demonstrated the highest efficacy from the first day of application, achieving a relative efficacy of 65.7%, significantly outperforming the Tondexir + Amyloland and Oxymatrine + Amyloland treatments, which recorded 48.6% and 41.3%, respectively.

By the third day after treatment, the Palizin + Amyloland mixture continued to exhibit superior control, reaching a relative efficacy of 93.6%, significantly higher than the other two treatments, which recorded 56.3% and 50.8%, respectively. This superiority persisted on the seventh and fourteenth days, as well as at 21 day post-treatment, with the Palizin + Amyloland combination achieving complete control (100%). In comparison, Tondexir + Amyloland and Oxymatrine + Amyloland reached 76.7%, 94.7%, 100% and 80.3%, 99.4%, 100%, respectively, at the same intervals.

The effectiveness of commercial bioinsecticides derived from *Bacillus* spp controlling plant insects is associated with the production of endospores and toxic crystal inclusions into the insect hosts (Patil et al., 2022). Khedher et al. (2015) revealed that *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* acts as larvicidal for *Tuta absoluta* by interacting between lipopeptides and the polyketide-based dipeptide that causes depolymerization of the insect's body wall. In another study, Khedher et al (2017) tested the same bacterium and reported that it could effectively negatively affect *Spodoptera littoralis* by disrupting the midgut integrity which in turn led to necrosis and disintegration of the basal lamina. In contrast, Tondexir + Amyloland, and Oxymatrine + Amylo-land was 76.7%, 94.7%, 100% and 80.3%, 99.4%, 100%, respectively, at the same time intervals.

There is a recently published study by Zhao et al. (2025), the *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* YJNbs21.10 showed insecticidal activity that reached the level close to the chemical insecticide, suggesting the potential biological control agent against aphids. In addition, the biological activity of macrolactin A towards aphid was assessed for the first time and an effective concentration against aphids was 169.02 mg/L was reported after 24h of exposure. These results provide a strong evidence of the application potential of the strain YJNbs21. 10 as a prospective biocontrol agent against the oat aphid *Rhopalosiphum padi*.

Table 3. Efficacy of Amyloland (*B. amyloliquefaciens*) at Varying Concentrations (2, 2.5, and 3 g/L) on *B. brassicae* Mortality at Different Post-Treatment Intervals

Note: LSD 0.05 :Concentrations = 9.12 Days = 12.62 Interaction = 21.86

Results of the synergy interaction revealed the growing effect of the Amyloland- plant-based insecticides combination over time. Total mortality (100%) was recorded for the Palizin + Amyloland blend 14 dpt and then for all mixtures at 21 dpt. Amyloland is a bioinsecticide that contains *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, clinically-tested for the production of biologically active substances targeting insect pests. It also produces diverse bioactive metabolites with insecticidal and antifungal effects (Malik et al., 2025). A report by Guadalup et al., (2019) also found in his observation *B. amyloliquefaciens* can be a potential biocontrol agent to manage *M. persicae* through suppression of its reproduction. This was the result of the bacterium's production of active enzymes that are insecticidal.

Conclusion

This study has proven the efficacy of plant-based and microbial insecticides against the cabbage aphid (*Brevicoryne brassicae*) with Palizin being the superior plant insecticide. The study also marked the significance of multiple control agents' interactions in synergy. Notably, the treatment by Palizin in combination with Amyloland resulted in the most efficient high mortality levels within a short period.

It is suggested that the integrated control with the botanical and bacterial insecticides is the best strategy on cabbage aphid. In particular, efforts should be put into combining Palizin and the bacterial bio-insecticide Amyloland, to achieve efficiency and to enhance the level of pest management in field situations.

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